

Palladium catalyzed cross-coupling reactions of organomercurials[†]

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Abstract : The palladium catalyzed cross-coupling reactions of methyl mercury iodide provide a mild, selective and general method for the construction of new C–C bond i.e. for the synthesis of arenes. The reaction proceeds in DMF, in the presence of a nucleophilic catalyst (iodide ion), at room temperature under argon atmosphere. Pd⁰ which is generated in the reaction mixture catalyzes the reaction. The catalytic cycle involved in the reaction consists of a sequence of *oxidative addition, transmetallation and reductive elimination* steps. The role played by the iodide ion as a nucleophilic catalyst is discussed. It forms an ionic complex (Pd⁰I)⁻ and therefore precipitation of palladium black is prohibited. Secondly the formation of ionic complex (CH₃HgI₂)⁻ helps the heterolytic fission of C–Hg bond in transmetallation step. Thus the selectivity of the reaction towards the expected product is enhanced.

Keywords : Palladium catalyzed reactions, cross-coupling reactions, organomercurials, C–C bond formation.

Introduction

Cross-coupling reactions of organometallics, catalyzed by transition metals, provide new methods for the construction of carbon-carbon bond. A number of reviews articles have been published which throw light on aspects of synthetic processes and transition metal based homogeneous catalysis used in C–C bond formation¹. Among the transition metals, palladium has created a huge interest in the catalytic reactions because it has well-established chemistry in (0), (II) and (IV) oxidation states, therefore, it is widely used as a catalyst in organic synthesis².

Among the organometallics, the organomercurials are less reactive as compared to organotins, organocoppers and Grignard reagents. The C–Hg bond is relatively non-polar and this makes organomercurials less reactive. However, organomercury compounds are usually stable in air, water, acid and heat. They can be synthesized by a number of synthetic routes³ and are also commercially available. They have been used extensively in organic synthesis⁴ for C–C bond formation due to their ease in undergoing transmetallation with aryl halides.

Organomercurials have ability to accommodate all important functional groups and they undergo a variety

of mild carbon-carbon bond forming reactions very easily. Kocovsky⁵ has recently summarized palladium-catalyzed reactions. These reactions include allylic oxidation, distereo- and enantio-controlled allylic substitution and transmetallation of organomercurials.

Palladium catalyzed acyldemetallation reactions of diorganomercurials with acyl halides and carbonylation reactions of alkylmercuryhalide with aryl halides, for the synthesis of unsymmetrical ketones in high yields, have been performed⁶. The reactions were carried out in the presence of a nucleophilic catalyst (iodide ion) at room temperature. Beletskaya *et al.*⁷ carried out the cross-coupling reactions of organomercurials with Ar(Het)X under argon atmosphere in the presence of palladium catalyst and nucleophilic catalyst (iodide ion) with high yields of the products. The low reactivity of organomercurials was easily overcome by transition metal and nucleophilic catalysis⁶. The palladium catalyzed cross-coupling reactions of diorganomercurials with aryl halides have been also reported⁸.

In the present communication, we report palladium catalyzed cross-coupling reactions of methyl mercury iodide with aryl halides as an important route for the synthesis of arenes (Reaction 1). The reaction proceeds se-

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lectively in DMF, in the presence of iodide ion as the nucleophilic catalyst at room temperature under argon atmosphere to give 73–82% yield (isolated) of the product.

R = *p*-O₂NC₆H₄, *p*-BrC₆H₄, *p*-ClC₆H₄, *p*-MeOC₆H₄, *p*-MeC₆H₄, C₆H₅

Pd = PdCl₂(C₆H₅CN)₂, PdCl₂(PPh₃)₂, PdBr₂(PPh₃)₂, Pd(OAc)₂(PPh₃)₂

I⁻ = NaI

Results and discussion

A number of experiments were performed to optimize the reaction conditions by changing catalyst and concentration of iodide ion. We found that the reaction proceeds selectively in the presence of Pd catalyst [PdCl₂(C₆H₅CN)₂, PdCl₂(PPh₃)₂, PdBr₂(PPh₃)₂, Pd(OAc)₂(PPh₃)₂] and iodide ion (2 equivalent of iodide ion based on Hg) in DMF to give 73–82% isolated yield of the product. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Pd⁰ is generated in the reaction mixture under reaction conditions (Scheme 1), which catalyzes the cross-coupling reaction⁶. The catalytic cycle involves a sequence of oxidative addition, transmetalation and reductive elimination steps⁸. In the oxidative addition step, R-I oxidatively adds to Pd⁰ and gives organopalladium intermediate, RPdI complex (step a). The RPdI complex further reacts with CH₃HgI by transmetalation to give RPdCH₃ complex (step b). Finally RPdCH₃ reductively eliminates

cross-coupling product RCH₃ with the recovery of Pd⁰ (step c).

Scheme 1. Generation of palladium(0) from palladium(II).

Scheme 2

Table 1. Reaction of CH₃HgI with aryl halide (DMF), catalyst (1 mole%), NaI (2 equivalent based on Hg), at room temperature, argon atmosphere

Entry no.	R	Catalyst	Reaction time (min)	Product	Yield (%) (isolated)
1.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	PdCl ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ CN) ₂	20	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	82
2.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	PdBr ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	20	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	80
3.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	PdCl ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	20	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	79
4.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Pd(OAc) ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	20	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	79
5.	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	PdCl ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ CN) ₂	30	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	75
6.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	PdCl ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ CN) ₂	30	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	78
7.	<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄	PdCl ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ CN) ₂	30	<i>p</i> -MeOC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	75
8.	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄	PdCl ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ CN) ₂	30	<i>p</i> -MeC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	75
9.	C ₆ H ₅	PdCl ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ CN) ₂	30	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	74

Functions of iodide ion :

Iodide ion plays an important role in cross coupling reaction (Scheme 3)⁶. It performs several functions in the reaction : (1) With CH_3HgI , iodide ion forms an ionic complex $(\text{CH}_3\text{HgI}_2)^-$ and therefore heterocyclic fission of C-Hg bond becomes easier in transmetallation step. (2) It forms an ionic complex $(\text{Pd}^0\text{I})^-$ with Pd^0 and hence precipitation of Pd black does not take place.

Scheme 3

Conclusion :

The reaction of CH_3HgI with aryl halide, in the presence of palladium catalyst and excess of iodide ion (nucleophilic catalyst) in DMF, provides a mild and selective method for the synthesis of arenes in high yields. The iodide ion avoids the precipitation of palladium black and favour the heterolytic fission of C-Hg bond in transmetallation step and therefore selectivity towards the expected product enhances.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Palladium catalysts $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CN})_2$ and $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ (Acros Chemicals), $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ (Lancaster) and $\text{PdBr}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ (Aldrich Chemicals) and CH_3HgI (Alfa Aesar Chemicals) were used. NaI was dried under vacuum for two hours before use. DMF was purified as per standard procedures and distilled before use.

IR spectra of the products were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrophotometer in the range 4000–600 cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian 300 MHz spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as the internal standard.

Cross-coupling reaction :

The reaction was carried out in 10 ml RB flask. 4 ml of DMF, NaI (2 mmol), aryl halide (1 mmol), CH_3HgI (1 mmol) and catalyst (0.01 mmol) (1 mole%) were placed in the flask and the slurry was stirred vigorously at room temperature under argon. The completion of reaction was

checked by TLC. The reaction mixture was then diluted by adding 10 ml water and extracted with 3×5 ml ether. The ether extracts were combined and washed with 2×5 ml of aqueous solution of NaI to remove traces of mercury salt from organic layer. The ether layer was then dried over MgSO_4 and evaporated under reduced pressure to obtain the product.

The physical constants⁹ and spectral (IR and NMR) data of acetophenones obtained are in accordance with the published data¹⁰

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More *et al.* : Palladium catalyzed cross-coupling reactions of organomercurials

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